

Fictional Media Hypothesis: A Potential Explanation of the Outcomes Paradox and Victor Tausk's Influencing Machine via Predictive Processing

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Predictive processing theory suggests that the brain uses both a top-down predictive process and a bottom-up sensory process. It is theorized the error between these two processes is constantly used to update belief models in weights called priors. This handshake is what is responsible for being able to correctly read paragraph of misspelled words. Your brain is constantly making predictions of what you are going to see, and it is being reconciled with your sensory data. When this prediction error becomes extremely large, it is theorized that the brain goes into alarm mode, struggles to reconcile sensory input with predictive outcomes, and causes visual and auditory hallucinations as well as delusional beliefs, the main hallmarks of psychosis. (Corlett, 2009).

An important empirical observation to take into consideration is the *outcomes paradox*: individuals with psychotic disorders often show better long-term outcomes in low- and middle-income countries than in high-income countries, despite reduced access to biomedical treatment (Padma, 2014). One possible contributing factor is the informational environment. In industrialized societies, individuals are surrounded by large amounts of fictional, symbolic, and highly stylized narratives through books, film, television, and digital media. These narratives are often not optimized to be in line with real-world constraints but instead viewer engagement. Another characteristic of this non-real-world constraint input is that it often structured, just in a way that is not conforming to real world constraints.

When 1223 people were followed from ages 5 months to 23 years, it was found that psychotic symptoms correlated with increasing and then decreasing computer use, as well as higher levels of video gaming and computer use. (Paqin, 2024)

Environmental and social adversity are associated with increased risk for psychotic disorders (Essock, 2017). Psychosis is also a common feature of many psychiatric, neuropsychiatric, neurologic, neurodevelopmental, and medical conditions (Calabrese et al., 2025), which reduce resilience. Alternatively interventions that reduce uncertainty and stabilize basic needs, such as secure housing (Tsemberis et al., 2004) have been shown to be able to reduce psychotic symptoms. Other interventions that stabilize metabolic or physiological resources exert similar effects. These findings are consistent with the hypothesis that psychosis is sensitive to perceived environmental risk rather than being solely the result of fixed biomedical pathology.

Prediction error is also known to increase in stressful situations, specifically aversive prediction error.(Robinson et. Al, 2013). Aversive prediction error is defined as when the reward your optimizing for, in this case safety is worse than expected. Appetitive prediction error is defined as when the reward you are optimizing for is better than expected. Research suggests that aversive error is learned faster than appetitive error and is given more precision weighting. Because safety is the reward optimized for, in aversive situations there is high precision of the reward being affected, so the brain learns these patterns faster. If non-real-world-conforming fictional patterns get learned in conjunction with aversive situations, these patterns could be weighted higher than they would be if not learned in an aversive experience. Depending on the type of game, games can also activate the stress system and increase the weighting of these patterns.

It is also known that by reading fiction, the default mode network is recruited and the brain learns from simulated experience. (Tamir et. Al, 2015). In the presence of psychological or physiological stressors, if salience is high perhaps even simulated patterns when reading can be trained onto priors with high precision, causing aberrant salience towards non-real-world conforming patterns.

This can be modeled with a predictive coding network.

— simulation results here -

Literature and media are products of specific political, economic, and historical contexts (Said, 1993). During the time period when novels started becoming more popular, and the printing press was invented, Cervantes' *Don Quixote* was written, a book about a man who loses his mind after reading too many chivalric romances. An interesting note here is the mentioning of the specific structure of the fictional media that Don Quixote interacted with. Specifically reading a lot of chivalric romances may impose some form of learned structure that is non-world conforming. The emergence of radio technologies coincides with a time period where delusional themes surrounded thought control, where this fictional information may be able to indirectly control thoughts through learning faulty simulated experiences. It has been mentioned by German Psychiatrist Victor Tausk that most patients at some point believe that an outside force is controlling their brain, often operated by a group of people that was persecuting them (Tausk, 1933). This could be viewed as a combination of paranoia or extreme risk aversion, and perhaps a correct assessment that an outside source was somehow effecting them.

Ultimately I hypothesize that exposure to non-real-world conforming fictional data during periods of stress causes the brain to learn these fictional patterns with too high of a precision weight. These experiences are traumatic and therefore highly salient. I hypothesize that aberrant salience is added to patterns picked up from non-real-world conforming fictional sources and it causes the brain to trust these incorrect predictions over sensory input, causing hallucinations and delusions, the hallmark symptoms of psychosis.

An interesting experiment design would be to raise children away from fictional material that is not bounded in reality. Fictional material was not common before the 1400's, however there are still ethical concerns such as impacts on creativity, as well as communication and social development with individuals who do not intake non-real-world structured fictional data.

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